

FIRE HAZARDS IN THE TECHNOSPHERE AND PRINCIPLES OF PROTECTION

Ashurova Laylo

Karshi Engineering and Economics Institute

Department of "Labor Protection and Technical Safety"

Senior Lecturer

ashurovalaylo83@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

This article discusses fires in the technosphere, their causes, fire prevention and technical measures, factors affecting the human body, and methods for extinguishing fires.

Keywords: Technosphere, fires, flame, hazardous and harmful factors, fire prevention, technical measures, products, synthetic materials, static charges, buildings and structures, thermal energy.

Relevance of the Topic

A fire is characterized by the uncontrolled and unauthorized burning of substances, materials, and gas-air mixtures outside a designated source, causing significant material damage and posing risks to people, objects, and transport systems.

The presence of combustible items, synthetic products, and various household appliances in technosphere elements increases the likelihood of fire while making even minor fires dangerous to human life and health. The burning of synthetic materials releases toxic gases.

Statistics show that nearly 90% of fire-related fatalities occur in residential buildings. Among them, up to 76% are due to poisoning by combustion products, and 19% result from thermal injuries caused by high temperatures. Electrical

appliances and household electrical devices account for 32.4% of all fires due to rule violations in their usage. Arson constitutes 10.2% of all fires in public buildings. The annual risk of fire-related fatalities is approximately 8×10^{-5} people, with a probability of death reaching up to 10^{-6} [11].

Statistical data indicate that people suffer from thermal burns, carbon monoxide poisoning, bleeding, and mechanical injuries due to a lack of knowledge on how to extinguish a fire in its initial phase and protect themselves. Therefore, every citizen must know how to act during a fire and be familiar with basic extinguishing methods (such as using water, sand, dense fabric, or special fire extinguishing agents). From this perspective, the relevance of this article is crucial for public awareness.

Objective of the Article

To analyze the factors causing fires in the technosphere and their impact on people, determine fire prevention measures, and develop recommendations for fire protection.

Tasks of the Research

- Analyzing fire-causing factors in the technosphere and their impact on people;
- Defining fire prevention measures and developing recommendations for fire protection.

Hazardous and Harmful Factors of Fires

Fires present various risks, including open flames, high temperatures affecting the environment and objects, toxic combustion products, smoke, reduced oxygen levels in the air, structural collapses, blast waves, flying debris, and harmful substances.

The severity of these factors depends on the fire duration (T), which is determined by the following formula:

$$T=N/v, \quad (1)$$

where:

- N = amount of combustible material (kg/m³);
- V = combustion rate of the material (kg/m³ per hour).

If a building contains various solid and liquid substances, and the building area-to-window area ratio is around 4:10, the fire duration is calculated using the following formula: [formula continuation needed].

$$T_e = C_g / 6C_0 (g_1/n_1 + g_2/n_2 + \dots + g_c/n_c) \quad (2)$$

where:

- **g** – the amount of each combustible substance (kg/m²);
- **n** – coefficient considering the combustion rate of materials (e.g., gasoline – 15, rubber and organic glass – 35, automobile tires – 40, wood – 65).

Factors Contributing to the Spread of Fires

The spread of fires can be caused by the following factors:

- Negligence in fire safety regulations;
- Carelessness in handling open flames;
- Failure to comply with operating rules for industrial equipment;
- Violation of technical safety rules when storing materials, leading to spontaneous combustion or ignition;
- Sparks generated by static electricity charges;
- Lightning discharges due to atmospheric electrical activity;
- Poor design, construction, and maintenance of buildings and structures;
- Cases of intentional arson.

Additionally, in residential buildings, fires are often caused by leaving children unsupervised or smoking indoors. In general, residential fires account for **52%** of all fire incidents. Therefore, children should not be left unattended, and they should not be allowed to play with matches, turn on electric heaters, or ignite gas appliances.

Fire Zones

A fire-affected area is conventionally divided into three zones:

1. **Active combustion zone (fire source)**
2. **Heat effect zone**
3. **Smoke formation zone [8]**

The active combustion zone includes flames, burning, or heated materials. Its destructive effect is primarily due to the high temperatures generated during combustion.

- Indoor temperatures in burning buildings can reach **800–900°C**.
- External fires can cause temperature rises of:
 - **1200–1350°C** for flammable gases
 - **1100–1300°C** for liquids
 - **1000–1250°C** for solid materials
 - **2000–3000°C** in cases of burning magnesium or electronics [9].

Toxic Effects of Fire

The intensity of heat radiation and increased air temperature can cause burns to the skin and respiratory tract. Additionally, fires release **50 to 100** different chemical compounds, leading to toxic effects on humans. The most dangerous and frequently encountered toxic substances in fires are **carbon monoxide (CO)** and **sulfur dioxide (SO₂)** [6].

Carbon monoxide (CO) is particularly dangerous because it binds to hemoglobin in the blood **200–300 times more readily than oxygen**, forming **carboxyhemoglobin (HbCO)**. As a result, oxygen deficiency occurs in the body, leading to life-threatening conditions.

Table 1

Various Levels of H₂O in Human Blood and Their Symptoms (%)

№	Impact Level (%)	Symptoms
1	0...10	No noticeable symptoms
2	10...20	Mild headache appears
3	20...30	Headache intensifies
4	30...40	Severe headache, weakness, dizziness, increased nausea and vomiting
5	40...50	Irregular heartbeat and increased breathing rate
6	50...60	Coma, loss of consciousness, rhythmic convulsions
7	60...70	Gradual biological death
8	70...80	Death within a few hours

Hazards of SO₂

Sulfur dioxide (SO₂) replaces oxygen in the bloodstream, accelerates breathing, and at dangerous concentrations, facilitates the inhalation of large amounts of other harmful gases.

Table 2

SO₂ Concentration in Inhaled Air and Its Symptoms (%)

№ Impact Level (%) Symptoms

1	0.5...4	Rapid breathing
2	5...7	Headache, rapid breathing, dizziness
3	10...12	Paralysis of the respiratory center, leading to biological death within minutes

Smoke and Its Effects

Smoke consists of microscopic solid particles formed from combustion products mixed with air.

Table 3**Smoke Volume Produced by the Combustion of 1 kg of Material (m³)****№ Material Smoke Volume (m³)**

1	Wood	4.9
2	Acetone	8.1
3	Rubber	10.8
4	Gasoline	12.6
5	Kerosene	12.8

Fire-resistant materials (brick, reinforced concrete) are considered the least hazardous in terms of fire risk, whereas buildings constructed with wooden structures pose the greatest danger. Additionally, the use of combustible thermal and soundproof materials, especially polymer materials, is highly dangerous.

According to statistical data, approximately one in ten fires in residential buildings, particularly in private and auxiliary buildings, occurs due to improper use of stoves.

Therefore, implementing legal, technical, and preventive fire safety measures in economic sectors and among the population is a national priority. Effective preventive measures can significantly reduce or prevent fires. Such efforts should primarily be focused on children and young people.

Fire is relentless, but people who are prepared, even with basic fire-extinguishing tools, can fight and overcome it. Our ancestors believed that fire could be extinguished with a glass of water in the first minute, a bucket in the second, and an entire reservoir in the third.

Special fire-resistant liquids are used for fire protection, applied to wood, fabrics, heat-resistant paints, and plasters. Fire-resistant compounds work by isolating the protected object from high temperatures. These measures do not prevent fire but enhance the fire resistance of the protected materials. Even steel load-bearing structures are not immune to fire damage under prolonged high temperatures.

For instance, wood is protected from fire using flame retardants (fire-resistant substances such as aluminum and magnesium hydroxides, ammonium phosphate and polyphosphate, molybdenum salts, vanadium, and germanium) and special coatings (such as alabaster and cement).

To prevent short circuits that may cause fires, electrical wires are insulated and laid only on non-combustible substrates.

Highly flammable and combustible liquids, as well as self-igniting and explosive substances, should not be stored in households. Existing ones should be kept in sealed containers, away from heating appliances, preventing spills and mechanical impacts. Special caution is required when handling household chemicals: they should not be disposed of in trash, mastics, varnishes, and aerosol cans should not be heated in an open flame, and clothing should not be washed with gasoline. Basic safety regulations must be followed.

Electric heating appliances should not be installed near combustible objects. Overloading the electrical network or leaving switched-on electrical appliances unattended is strictly prohibited. Their operation must fully comply with manuals and instructions.

Blocking access roads to buildings, obstructing routes to fire hydrants, locking doors of general corridors in multi-story buildings, and restricting access to emergency exits are all forbidden. Fire safety systems and fire extinguishing equipment should be regularly checked and maintained to prevent fires or minimize their consequences.

The interior walls, partitions, and ceilings of category V buildings should be coated with plaster, protective paints, or varnishes. Load-bearing structures in stationary enclosed sports facilities that can accommodate more than 600 spectators must be made of non-combustible or highly fire-resistant materials that can withstand at least 0.75 hours. For stationary structures with a capacity of fewer than 300 spectators, if combustible materials are used, their fire resistance must be at least 0.25 hours. Club and theater stages accommodating 800 or more seats must be protected by fire curtains, and the wooden flooring of the stage must be deeply impregnated with fire-resistant agents.

Fire curtains must have a fire resistance limit of at least one hour, be heat-insulated, non-combustible, and made of materials that do not release harmful decomposition by-products.

Closed halls of auditoriums and sports facilities with up to 1,500 seats, as well as conference halls, should be decorated with highly fire-resistant materials. If the seating capacity exceeds 1,500, or in archives, libraries, and storage rooms of catalogs and inventories, only non-combustible finishing materials should be used.

Fire-resistant roof panels are divided into three types: those with a fire resistance of at least 2.5 hours (Type 1), at least 1 hour (Type 2), and at least 0.75 hours (Type 3). They are made from non-combustible materials and serve to prevent the spread of fire between building floors during the required fire resistance period.

The increasing number of high-rise residential buildings and the need for their fire protection have become even more relevant. The fire hazard in high-rise buildings is exacerbated by the presence of other facilities within them (such as retail stores, communication centers, public services, and catering establishments). In such buildings, fires spread vertically through stairwells and elevator shafts.

Rescue operations in high-rise buildings are particularly challenging. Fire spreads vertically at a speed of 10 meters per minute or more. Within a few minutes,

the entire building can be engulfed in smoke, making breathing difficult. The most intense smoke accumulates on upper floors. Additionally, in many high-rise residential buildings, the lack of proper fire detection systems delays fire identification.

The amount of water required to extinguish a large fire can be determined using the following formula:

$$Q = 3,6 \times q \times t_n \quad (4)$$

In this case, t_n is the calculated duration of the fire, and q is the water consumption in L/s.

Public buildings encompass a wide range of multi-sectoral structures that differ based on the number of people present, the amount of fire load, and the nature (mode) of operation. Furthermore, these characteristics require a differentiated approach to addressing fire safety issues in each case.

Factors contributing to fatalities in public buildings include the presence of materials saturated with highly hazardous substances (HI, HN, etc.) that are released during combustion, as well as the increasing number of various energy sources. In recent years, fire incidents in public buildings caused by negligence have accounted for an average of 36.5% of all cases.

From the perspective of protecting material assets within a building, it is essential to consider not only the expected financial damage but also the social significance of the potential losses caused by fire. This is especially relevant for buildings housing museums, archives, libraries, as well as historical and architectural monuments.

Undoubtedly, quantitative methods for assessing fire hazards in public buildings must take into account the combustion processes within the structure, evacuation methods for people, and factors that characterize the likelihood of

emergencies. Among fatal fire-related incidents, smoke inhalation remains the leading cause of death.

In the event of a fire, individuals should immediately exit the building using the primary or emergency (fire) exits or staircases and notify the fire department as soon as possible. If feasible, efforts should be made to extinguish the fire in its early stages using available means such as fire extinguishers, indoor fire hydrants, blankets, sand, water, etc.

It is important to remember that fires involving electrical supply elements should not be extinguished with water. In such cases, the power supply should first be disconnected before attempting to put out the fire. If all efforts prove unsuccessful and the fire continues to spread, one must take all necessary safety measures and evacuate the building without delay.

When rescuing victims from a burning building, it is recommended to cover the head with a wet blanket (coat, raincoat, or thick fabric) before entering. To prevent sudden flare-ups, doors should be opened cautiously to avoid a rapid influx of fresh air. In heavily smoke-filled rooms, it is advisable to crawl or stay low while breathing through a damp cloth. If a person's clothing catches fire, it can be extinguished by covering them with a blanket (or coat) to cut off the oxygen supply. After rescuing the victim, first aid should be administered, and they should be transported to the nearest medical facility as soon as possible. [5]

Figure 1. Methods of Assisting a Person Trapped in a Fire

In fire protection of buildings and structures, fire extinguishing equipment plays a crucial role. Fire extinguishing tools include materials such as sand, water, fire blankets, and standard equipment like fire extinguishers, axes, hooks, and buckets.

Fire-fighting foams are designed for extinguishing fires and are categorized into chemical foams (OP fire suppression agents) and air-mechanical foams (OVP fire suppression agents). These foams are used for extinguishing various flammable substances and materials that burn without air access; however, they are not suitable for use on energized electrical installations.

2nd Image. Fire Extinguishers (Ognetushitel)

Carbon Dioxide Fire Suppression Devices (OU). These are designed to extinguish fires involving various materials that cannot burn without exposure to air, as well as fires in electrical networks, transportation, and electrical installations with voltages not exceeding 10,000 V.

The required number of fire extinguishers for industrial buildings is determined as follows:

$$n_0 = m_0 \times S \quad (5)$$

Here, **S** represents the area of the production room in square meters (**m²**), and

m_0 is the standard number of fire extinguishers required per 1 m^2 .

Carbon dioxide fire suppression devices are classified into **manual** (OU-2, OU-3, OU-5, OU-6, OU-8), **mobile** (OU-24, OU-80, OU-400), and **stationary** (OSU-5) types.

The **fire alarm system** is a set of technical devices designed to detect fire factors, generate and transmit fire alarms, and collect, process, record, and communicate other relevant information. Depending on the type of active substances used, automatic fire extinguishing systems can include **gas, powder, foam, or aerosol** suppression methods.

3rd Image: **Fire Detection System**

For example, "foam" refers to water supply under high pressure. It is highly suitable for protecting oil product storage facilities. "Powder" is represented by spraying special powder in enterprises where high-tech electrical equipment is installed. "Aerosol" is easy to use, autonomous, does not require additional devices, is easy to assemble, and is safe for people.

Based on the above-mentioned factors, we can conclude the following: The presented material indicates that fires not only destroy material assets but also cause serious harm to human life and health and pollute the environment. The faster society, science, and technology develop, the more pressing the problem of fires

and fire safety remains. Just as humans are not fully protected from dangers, they are also not fully protected from fires. Since any technology and equipment are operated by humans, errors inevitably occur, leading to fires. However, we can minimize the risk of fires in the technosphere and reduce their consequences.

Complying with fire safety rules, taking preventive measures, and knowing how to protect oneself and others from fires are human responsibilities. Safeguarding one's life and the lives of others should be the primary duty of every citizen, as it is the greatest value on our planet!

List of References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Fire Safety" (1993).
2. GOST 12.1.004-91 - "Fire Safety. General Requirements."
3. QMQ II-89-80 "Master Plan of Industrial Enterprises."
4. GOST 12.3.042-88 - "Woodworking Industry. General Safety Requirements."
5. Dunay V.I. First Aid for the Population in Emergency Situations. Student Guide. - Minsk: BGU, 2011. - 139 pages.
6. Xolbayev B.M., Raximov O.D., Maxmatqulov N.I. Life Safety. Textbook (Part 2). - Tashkent: "Voriz-Nashriyot," 2020. 304 pages.
7. Fires and Fire Safety in 2018: Statistical Report. Edited by D.M. Gordiyenko. - Moscow: VNIPO, 2019, - 125 pages.
8. Maxmatqulov N.I. Assessing Technosphere Safety Based on Mathematical Modeling. Monograph. - Qarshi: "Intellect" Publishing House, 2022, 133 pages.
9. Maxmatqulov N.I. "Correct Behavior of the Population in Emergency Situations" Article. International Journal of Advanced Research in Education, Technology, and Management. Vol.2, Issue 9.- 175 pages.

- 10.Maxmatqulov N.I. "Fire as a Factor of Technogenic Disaster" Article.
International Journal of Advanced Research in Education, Technology, and
Management. Vol.2, Issue 9.- 175 pages.
- 11.<https://bank.nauchniestati.ru/primery/referat-na-temu-pozhary-zdaniy-i-sooruzhenij/>